

Redefining Reading Assessment through the Use of AI-Harnessed App “Readlee”

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ABSTRACT: Reading is paramount in English language acquisition, especially in the Pakistani ESL context because it is a source of linguistic input. So far, reading assessment has been undergoing diversifying scenarios, but still, there is a need to explore and experiment with new things like AI-based apps to come up with applicable solutions to the issue. Thus, the current study integrated an AI-harnessed application, “Readlee” to assess college students reading fluency through an automated feedback system. 40 college-level ESL students participated in the study. They were made to read English text aloud through the AI-Based application “Readlee” which recorded their loud reading and produced results on the basis of Word Count per Minute (WCPM). The results were then analyzed quantitatively and presented in tabular forms. Furthermore, the performances of the students were compared with one another for which graphs were used. The effectiveness of the Readlee App to teach and assess reading fluency was qualitatively analyzed on the basis of the features of the app which were tested in this study. The results showed that the Readlee App is effective in teaching and assessing reading fluency at the college level. Moreover, the results showed that students had different reading paces though the minimum WCPM was 38 and the maximum was 153. Thus, the study recommended the use of the Readlee App to teach and assess reading fluency at college level.

Keywords: Teaching and assessing reading fluency, automated feedback system, AI-Based Application “Readlee”, Word Count per Minute

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1. Introduction

The important role of reading in education has been emphasized by several scholars because reading is incremental to language learning. It is through reading that one reaches the heightening of knowledge and information. The important role of reading in education is universally acknowledged but its importance in language teaching and learning is even more significant because maximum of linguistic input is infused through reading. However, practicing reading without appropriate assessment hinders language learning on one hand and assessing students’ reading in a setting like Pakistani English language classroom is also challenging on the other hand. So far, reading assessment has been undergoing

diversifying scenarios, but still, there is a need to explore and experiment with new things like AI-based apps to come up with applicable solutions to the issue. Thus, the current study integrates an AI-harnessed application, "Readlee" to assess college students' reading fluency through an automated feedback system to redefine the reading assessment.

The important role of reading in education has been emphasized by several scholars. Woudenberg (2018) asserts that none of us can deny the importance of reading in our lives because reading is a source of knowledge and every storehouse of knowledge is reached through reading. But, as far as the issues pertaining to reading are concerned, Grabe (2009) indicates that reading is a complex phenomenon that involves further complex cognitive processes. Moreover, different researches indicate that many readers especially ESL readers face severe problems in reading which cause hindrance in their reading pace and comprehension. These problems pertain to vocabulary, sentence structure, background knowledge, cultural knowledge, and knowledge of text type (Chawwang, 2008).

According to Sinambela (2017), low or less exposure to the target language causes hindrances in acquiring reading skills for ESL students. This indicates that reading fluency and comprehension can be improved through maximum exposure to the target language (Iwahori, 2008). Al Zoubi (2018:5) also admits that there is a "statistically significant correlation between exposure to language and developing the four language skills". Wen-Cheng, Chien-Hung, & Chung-Chieh (2011:4) indicate that in most of the countries where English is learned and taught as a second or foreign language, textbooks are used in the classrooms to give exposure to the target language. In the Pakistani educational setting, English is taught as a compulsory subject up to graduation level and specific textbooks as prescribed by the curriculum wing, textbook board and educational authorities are used at varying levels of education (Panzai & Channa, 2017:4).

Rasinski (2004) claims that assessing reading fluency is a difficult job because it takes a lot of time especially when the teacher has a large class. Moreover, finding a reliable and objective scale to assess reading fluency is also tough. But, this issue has been resolved to some extent because of digital platforms and different types of computer software (Morrison & Wilcox 2020:10). The use of new technology in the educational context is becoming a fashion in the modern world. Thus, the application of AI to language teaching and assessment is becoming vital because it has solved many problems of language teaching and assessment by simulating human intelligence in teaching-learning activities (Dai & Ke 2022). Walker et al. (2007:30) assert that AI applications are beneficial for creating written texts, developing students' skills in constructing sentences or building up texts, and practicing writing and reading skills. Moreover, Lotze (2016) also opines that the application of AI systems to language teaching helps teachers by enabling them to develop systems through which all the learning requirements are fulfilled. Then, Ahmadi (2018:3) favors the idea of using new technology in language teaching because it is fruitful in developing language skills. Radwan (2017) also posits that the use of AI can solve many issues pertaining to teaching/learning English.

Since assessing reading fluency is one of the key jobs of an English language teacher, this study recommends using an AI-based application named "Readlee" to provide quick and automated feedback to teachers and students alike. It gives the statistics about

the words assigned, total reading time and word count per minute. The app is mobile/tab/computer-friendly and ESL readers can use it according to the means they have. "Readlee" is a new application for mobiles/tablets/laptops/computers and it uses artificial intelligence to improve literacy. It's a Co-designed software by two teachers, Steve Askar and Drew Madson to personalize reading instruction for learners; the software listens to students read any text out loud and immediately provides them with personalized feedback. Children read out loud to the app on a smartphone, laptop or tablet, and Readlee tracks factors such as pacing and accuracy, providing real-time feedback. Readlee won the Harvard Innovation Lab Social Impact Award shortly after it was launched, and it has been tested in various U.S. schools.

2. Statement of the Problem

Assessment in reading is a fundamental socket to plugin the learning but the traditional reading assessment has numerous pitfalls like large-sized classes, time constraints, lack of resources and subjective biases. All these issues underscore the incorporation of innovative and automated assessment and feedback systems into the teaching of reading especially in the Pakistani ESL context. Thus, the current study uses a transformative AI-powered reading assessment tool for quick, timely and personalized reading evaluation.

3. The Rationale of the Study

According to Naviwala (2016), 75% of Pakistani students cannot read English text properly. Poor reading skills cause students' failure in writing as well because reading is a source of language input and output in form of writing, cannot be guaranteed without effective reading. Though English language teachers try their level best to develop reading skills in learners, yet learners' ability to read successfully remains a dream. Moreover, teachers cannot make the students read during the class because this activity needs a lot of time as the classes are crowded and there are so many students in the class. Neither the teacher can make the students practice reading nor can he assess their reading skills. Thus, new techniques and methods are required to teach and assess reading skills to have better learning outcomes. So, the current study has incorporated the use of "Readlee" an AI-Based application to assess the reading fluency of college-level ESL learners and give them automated and personalized feedback so that they may improve their reading skills and teacher may monitor their time-to-time progress in reading proficiency.

The current study had a three-fold purpose. Firstly, it endeavored to try a digital and automated feedback system to assess and evaluate the reading pace and fluency of college-level ESL learners. Secondly, it investigated how far the ESL students differ from one another in reading pace on the basis of word count per minute (WCPM). Thirdly, the study intended to estimate how effective would be the use of the Readlee application to assess the reading pace of ESL learners on the basis of WCPM. Since the study aimed to achieve three objectives, it attempted to seek answers to the following research questions:

Research Questions

The current study endeavored to seek answers to the following research questions:

1. What is the average reading pace of college ESL students when they read English text?
2. How far do the ESL students differ from one another in terms of reading fluency based on Word Count per Minute (WCPM)?
3. How much effective is the use of Readlee app in assessing and improving the English reading skills of college-level ESL learners?

4. Theoretical Framework

The current study followed Grabe's (2009) theory on reading which covers the notions of reading like reading fluency, and comprehension. According to Grabe, reading is a complex and convoluted process that further involves mental and cognitive processes which are concerned with reading fluency and comprehension. Grabe indicates that a reader needs to develop higher and lower levels of reading skills to be an efficient reader. The lower-level skills include reading, fluency, word processing, vocabulary, grammar knowledge, meaning encoding and inference whereas the higher-level skills consist of inference and comprehension. The following diagram (Figure 1), can be considered to have an understanding of the higher and the lower level reading skills.

Figure 1: Reading Skills

The current study followed Grabe's theory of reading because it systematically covers all the important aspects of reading. Though our focus was only on reading fluency, yet it is an important element in reading, and it is significantly correlated with other elements like pronunciation and comprehension.

5. Literature Review

The current study aimed at redefining and revolutionizing the teaching of reading and its assessment at the college level in the Pakistani ESL context. The key focus was on three important aspects including average reading pace among the readers, variation in the score made for the readers and effectiveness of the AI-powered App “Readlee” for assessing the reading skills of English language learners at the college level. Thus, the following literature was reviewed to analyze what techniques and methods have been followed to assess reading so far in an educational setting and what else can be tried to redefine reading fluency assessment and teaching of reading:

Traditional Teaching and Assessment of Reading

Hudson, Lane and Pullen (2005:58) also provided a checklist to assess reading prosody. This checklist focuses on the following key features:

- Student placed vocal emphasis on appropriate words.
- Student's voice tone rose and fell at appropriate points in the text.
- Student's inflection reflected the punctuation in the text (e.g., voice tone rose near the end of a question).
- In narrative text with dialogue, the student used appropriate vocal tone to represent characters' mental states, such as excitement, sadness, fear, or confidence.
- Student used punctuation to pause appropriately at phrase boundaries.
- Student used prepositional phrases to pause appropriately at phrase boundaries.
- Student used subject-verb divisions to pause appropriately at phrase boundaries.
- Student used conjunctions to pause appropriately at phrase boundaries.

To assess and understand reading fluency, Hasbrouck (2006) introduced us to a four-level scale to assess reading prosody. It was first developed for the 1992 National Assessment of Educational Progress. The scale can be understood well through the following table see Table 1.

Table 1: Reading Quality Assessment

Level	Rate	Description
4	Fluent	Reads primarily in larger, meaningful phrase groups. Although some regressions, repetitions and deviations from text may be present, these do not appear to detract from the overall structure of the story. Preservation of the author's syntax is consistent. Some or most of the story is read with expressive interpretation.
3	Fluent	Reads primarily in three- or four-word phrase groups. Some small groupings may be present. However, the majority of phrasing seems appropriate and preserves the syntax of the author. Little or no expressive interpretation is present.
2	Non-fluent	Reads primarily in two-word phrases with some three- or four-word groupings. Some word-by-word reading may be present. Word groupings may seem awkward and unrelated to larger context of sentence or passage.
1	Non-fluent	Reads primarily word-by-word. Occasional two-word or three-word phrases may occur but these are infrequent and/or they do not preserve meaningful syntax.

The study introduced us to two methods to analyze reading prosody. Four-level scale and checklist to assess reading prosody are reliable tools according to this study. Our study in contrast to this study used an AI-Based app to analyze the reading fluency of ESL students at the college level which analyses the reading fluency on the basis of WCPM using digital resources and artificial intelligence.

Iwahori, (2008) experimented with extensive reading activities to develop reading fluency in L2 English language learners at the high school level in Japan. The readers were provided with comic books to read so that they might not lose interest in reading and the material might amuse them. Pre and post-tests were conducted to rate the reading pace of the research participants. The results indicated that the readers made a considerable improvement and extensive reading through comic books proved useful for developing reading fluency in Japanese High school English language learners.

The study introduces the use of comic books as extensive material to develop reading fluency in High school English language learners. The common element in this study and our study is the development of reading skills but, our study in contrast to this one used the textbook as reading material through an AI-Based application instead of comic books.

Klemek (2017) analyzed the efficacy of two reading strategies to improve the reading fluency of first-grade English language learners through Repeated and Shared Reading. The study period was six weeks during which both of the reading strategies were tried and improvement in fluency was also recorded for the purpose of analysis. The research findings indicated that Shared Reading proved more effective as compared to Repeated Reading.

The study came up with the recommendations that Shared Reading is a useful tool to improve the reading fluency of English language learners. In contrast to this study, our study tried to improve the reading fluency of college English language learners through an automated system of feedback through the use of an AI-Based application.

Sinambela (2017:8) used Prosody as a tool to assess the reading fluency of adult ESL students. The study analyzed the reliability prosody as a tool to assess the reading fluency of English language learners in Indonesia. Undergraduate female and male English language learners were the participants of this study. The students were made to read aloud and their reading was taped. Then it was measured using the Multidimensional Fluency Scale and comprehension was tested through a standardized test. The research findings indicated that prosody is a reliable tool to assess reading fluency and comprehension. Moreover, the study indicated that low exposure to the target language is a key reason to acquire the prosodic reading skill in ESL students.

The study recommended the use of prosody as a reliable tool to assess reading fluency. Our study also analyzed the reliability and validity of a tool to assess reading fluency but in contrast to this study, our study analyzed a digital tool that automatically assesses reading fluency and gives automated feedback to the teacher and student alike.

Geva, Garrison and Mak (2019) presented an overview of theory and research about second language reading development in learners with reading difficulties. The

researchers further informed about the implication of this research for the development of reading assessment strategies that are valid and reliable along with being culturally and linguistically sensitive. The study highlighted that for L2 learners, phonological awareness, working memory and rapid automated naming are very important for the development of reading skills. Moreover, early-grade L2 learners can develop reading skills at a considerable level during the development of their oral language proficiency. The study indicated that oral language proficiency is supportive in developing comprehension skills in L2 language learners. The study also indicated that cognitive skills measured in L1 are reliable to use for diagnosing L2 reading disability in case the reader is persistently not fluent as compared to other readers of the same background.

The study is significant because it has covered an important aspect of reading development in L2 learners with reading difficulty. In contrast to the study, our study is concerned with reading practice and assessment through AI-Based application.

Aldhanhani & Abu-Ayyash (2021:9) conducted a study in United Arab Emirates (UAE) to analyze teaching and assessment strategies to improve oral reading fluency of English language learners. An exploratory qualitative design was adopted for this study. The study used document analysis, classroom observations and interviews to investigate the issue in two private schools in UAE. The study had a three-fold purpose including the identification of oral reading strategies used in private schools, assessment strategies and a match between reading aloud and assessment strategies. The study findings indicated that teachers used different reading-aloud strategies like repeated reading, assisted reading, pair reading, individual reading aloud, practice reading, coral reading, reading practice and assisted reading to enhance oral reading fluency. Moreover, the study highlighted that like different reading strategies, teachers used different strategies to assess students' oral reading fluency including the rubric, checklist, DIBLES: WCPM test, word efficiency test and keeping records of students' performance. The study also analyzed the effectiveness of these strategies indicating that these strategies were useful and suitable to teach and assess reading fluency.

This study only analyzed the strategies different teachers used for teaching and assessing oral reading fluency and indicated that they were useful for teaching and assessment purposes. In contrast to this study, our study incorporated the use of an AI-Based app named Readlee to assess and improve the reading skills of college-level ESL students.

Technology-based Teaching and Assessment of Reading

In comparison to traditional and manual ways of teaching and assessing reading, modern methods are being welcomed in ELT. These methods incorporate the use of technology, digital platforms and different Apps. For instance, Klimova, & Zamborova (2020:10) indicated that mobile apps are very useful in improving reading skills and level of comprehension. The authors postulated that reading acquisition is crucial for language learners otherwise they cannot acquire knowledge. Thus, the study highlighted the effectiveness of mobile apps for acquiring reading skills. For this, the study reviewed the existing literature and indicated that the use of apps for acquiring reading skills is more effective than the traditional and conventional ways. Moreover, the motivation level of

students was also found to be improving using mobile apps to improve comprehension skills.

Özbek, & Ergül (2022:37) measured the effectiveness of the Comprehension Strategies Mobile App (COSMA) for teaching reading comprehension to students with learning disabilities. The experiment was made with four students including three male and 1 female student. Students' performance in reading was assessed through tests with multiple-choice questions. Moreover, students' use of strategies was assessed through on-task metacognitive interviews. The study indicated that COSMA is effective and has a positive impact on learner's performance in reading comprehension. Moreover, the students were found to be motivated while using the App. So, this study also favors the use of mobile apps for developing reading comprehension.

Ostiz, Bernacer, Garcia, Diaz-Sanchez, Rello, Lallier & Arrondo (2021) reviewed the literature on the use of electronic interventions in teaching and learning of reading skills. The study focused on randomized controlled trials and quasi-experimental studies in which electronic tools were used to improve reading skills. The study included 55 pieces of research that incorporated electronic tools to improve the reading skills of the learners and it was found that thirty-three different electronic tools were used to develop reading skills among the language learners, though most of them were in English and focused on first language of the language learners. But it's pertinent to say that the studies were quite different from one another in nature and scope. The study finally indicated that the use of electronic tools in the teaching of reading is effective so it should be incorporated in the teaching of reading.

Maulida, Ivone & Wulyani (2021) indicated that course books have limited knowledge about social and natural science for high school students so, the students need supplementary material to fulfill their needs. To solve the problem, the study introduced the Readread mobile application-based supplementary material to improve learners' comprehension skills. The formative evaluation of the app indicated that the feedback was positive, and it was found that relevant supplementary material was useful whereas multimedia aspects were additionally effective in solving the problems. Moreover, the students also gave positive feedback for the app and suggested that more material should be added to the app so that the learners might enjoy more individualized and personalized learning in the area of reading.

Thus, the literature on digital and electronic tools indicated that traditional ways to teach and assess reading are being replaced with new ones that are more effective and idealized. The transformation from manual to digital platforms to learn and teach reading skills is remarkable and encouraging. Thus, we also incorporated the use of AI-harnessed App to teach and assess reading skills at college in the Pakistani ELT context.

All the above-cited works were done in the area of teaching and assessment of reading fluency in various situations using different tools, strategies and methods. The review of this literature indicated that various tools and methods have been used to analyze reading fluency but studies that incorporate the use of digital platforms and AI-Based tools to analyze reading fluency are scarce. So, the current study incorporated the use of an AI-powered tool to teach and assess reading fluency at college. Moreover, the study

endeavored to suggest an innovative and effective method to redefine the teaching and assessment of the reading skills in the Pakistani ESL context.

6. Research Methodology

The current study followed the quantitative research paradigm. 40 college-level ESL learners were made to read English text through the Readlee app and the results provided by the app were noted for further processes. The students were made to read a chapter from their English textbook, and they were required to read the text at their home through their mobile phones using the Readlee app. The students were asked to make their Readlee accounts separately and join Readlee Class using the link and class code as shared by the teacher. Moreover, they were also given proper training to use the app in their mobiles and to submit their reading task through the app.

6.1 Site for the Research

The current research was conducted at the Government Associate College of Commerce, Kahuta, District Rawalpindi, Pakistan. It was a public sector college where English was taught as a compulsory subject and the students were taught English using two textbooks. The students had 10 to 12 years' English language learning background and during all these years, they were taught English through prescribed textbooks.

6.2 Data Collection

The research data were quantitatively collected through the Readlee app by assigning the students a reading task. The students were required to read the text aloud to the Readlee app. After they had read the text, the app provided the Word Count per Minute (WCPM) through excel sheet which was used for further procedures, analysis and comparisons.

6.3 Data Analysis

The research data sought through the Readlee app was analyzed using both qualitative and quantitative techniques. The Readlee app was used as a tool to count and analyze the word count per minute quantitatively. Then, quantitative data in form of numbers were analyzed through percentages and graphs whereas the effectiveness of the app for assessing and improving the reading pace of college-level ESL learners was analyzed qualitatively.

6.4 Ethical Considerations

Since the research was conducted in human society, it needed to tackle ethical issues carefully. So, the participants of the study gave their consent to be a part of this research through an informed consent letter. They were not forced to be a part of this research. The identity of the participants was not disclosed anywhere in the study. Thus, pseudonyms were used to discuss the performances of the students in the reading task. To make students feel convenient during the reading, they were allowed to read the assign text at home in solitude so that they might not feel shy or lose confidence while reading to the audience. To ensure that students time is not wasted and they don't indulge in any irrelevant activity that might cause academic loss to the learners, they were asked to read the same text from their textbook which they had to read manually as their daily reading

task for the subject of English. Moreover, they were asked to share their reservations in terms of the availability of the resources like mobile, tablet, laptop/computer and internet. Those who lacked resources were offered to use them at college using college computer lab which was furnished with computers and internet. Thus, it was ensured that no mental, physical or financial issues/loss arise for the students after participating in the research.

7. Data Analysis

The key focus of the study was to come up with a calculation and word count per minute after the students had read a given text. Thus, the data were primarily analyzed using Readlee App. 40 college-level English language learners participated in this study. They were assigned a reading task (consisting of 694 words) from their textbook of English. All of the participants read the given text through the Readlee App and their performance in form of word count per minute was sought through the statistics provided by the app through excel spread sheet.

The detail of the performance is presented in the following table which consists of further information about the reading pace of the learners in the form of word count per minute and informs about the total words assigned to the students (see table 2).

Table 2: Students Reading Word Count per Minute

Participant No.	WCPM	Words Assigned	Participant No.	WCPM	Words Assigned
1	119	694	21	106	694
2	70	694	22	89	694
3	64	694	23	89	694
4	97	694	24	95	694
5	131	694	25	153	694
6	96	694	26	88	694
7	104	694	27	38	694
8	96	694	28	57	694
9	116	694	29	115	694
10	97	694	30	126	694
11	94	694	31	120	694
12	116	694	32	78	694
13	135	694	33	65	694
14	50	694	34	88	694
15	115	694	35	87	694
16	122	694	36	81	694
17	82	694	37	76	694
18	66	694	38	67	694
19	109	694	39	95	694
20	119	694	40	71	694

The table indicates that the participants could read words at varying pace and all of them could read a varying number of words per minute. The same data have been bifurcated into five different levels to further describe the range of the words read per

minute by the participants to have an idea of how far the performances differ from one another.

The following table (see table 3) describes the range in which the participants could read. It also gives the number of students in who performed within range 1 to 5.

Table 3. Students' Range of Performance in Reading Pace

Range 1 WCPM	Range 2 WCPM	Range 3 WCPM	Range 4 WCPM	Range 5 WCPM
38	64	81	104	122
50	65	82	106	126
57	66	84	109	131
	67	87	115	135
	70	88	115	153
	71	88	116	
	76	89	116	
	78	89	119	
		94	120	
		95		
		95		
		96		
		96		
		97		
		97		

The data indicated that only three participants were found to be able to read words under the range 1 which counted the words from 38 to 60 per minute. Whereas only eight out of forty participants could read words in the range 2 which was from 60 to 80 words per minute. Fifteen participants could read under range 3 which was from 81 to 100 words per minute. Nine of the participants were able to read under range 4 which has the range of 100-120 words per minute whereas only five participants read under range 5 which was from 122 to 153 words per minute.

8. Discussion and Findings

These statistics indicate that only 12.5 % of the participants could read at the fastest pace as compared to other participants. But, if the performances of these 5 participants are compared, the lowest score remains 122 words per minute whereas the highest score is 153, which means that the lowest scorer in this range is still lagging behind the top scorer. Then 22.5% of the participants could read in between 101 to 120 words per minute. These nine participants scored differently though some of them had the same scores. This range of their score indicates that their performance was not poor but they could improve more to reach the highest score. Significantly, 37.5% of the participants scored under the 3rd range which ranges from 81 to 100 words per minute. As compared to other ranges, the largest number of the research participants read the text at a mediocre level. The participants in this range were found to be neither too poor in reading pace nor were they too strong and fast in reading. Thus, it can be asserted that most of the students can read English text at a mediocre level in comparison to their peers. Then, 20% of the participants were found to

read under the range 2 which consists of 61 to 80 words per minute. This performance cannot be regarded as ideal or exemplary if it is compared with other ranges namely three, four and five. 7.5 of the participants could read under range 1 ranging from 38 to 60 words per minute. Thus, the following graph (see Figure 2) can be considered to understand the performance of the participants.

Figure 2: Range of Words Read per Minute.

9. Effectiveness of the Readlee app

The research indicated that the Readlee app is effective in assessing ESL readers' reading fluency, accuracy and total reading time. Moreover, it has a rich inbuilt library that has ample literary books consisting of texts on poetry, essays, plays, short stories, novels and speeches as per the needs and tastes of the ESL readers. However, the current study used the option of uploading the text of the teacher's choice so that academic purposes could be achieved, and the students could be made to read the textbooks included in their syllabus. The automated feedback by the app to the teacher and learners indicated that quick and personalized feedback enabled the teacher to know learners' weaknesses and the learners also got a chance to know about their shortcomings and weaknesses. According to Stuart (2004:1), timely and quick feedback is paramount in the teaching and learning process for progress. So, the data indicated that if Readlee is used for English language teaching in the educational context, quick and personalized feedback can be ensured.

The findings of the study indicated that the Readlee app supports an ESL teacher in many ways but the most remarkable one is that through which a teacher can upload a reading task and the student can read the text and submit his tasks accordingly. Large-sized classrooms hamper the teacher from conducting reading in the classroom. Thus, the reading practice of the learners is neglected in the class. Moreover, the teacher assigns reading tasks to the students at home but most of them don't read at home but they claim that they have read the text at home. Previously, there existed no proper system through

which a teacher could know whether the students had read the assigned text or not. However, the current study indicated that Readlee has solved this problem and has provided the language teachers with a platform where they can assign reading tasks and monitor students' reading activities on a regular basis with automated feedback, a complete record of task submission, recording of the loud reading, login time/date and so on.

Thus, it can be asserted that the Readlee app is quite helpful in teaching and learning the English language as it provides automated feedback to the students and the teacher alike. Moreover, the study produced positive results in redefining teaching and reading fluency assessment in the area of ELT in the Pakistani educational context.

10. Conclusion

Reading has a vital role in language learning and teaching but previously there existed no suitable system to assess reading objectively. Moreover, language teachers needed some system that could support them in making students read on regular basis to improve their reading fluency and comprehension. The current study has indicated that the use of the Readlee app has solved many issues pertaining to teaching reading. It was a study with three fold-purpose which focused on testing a digital and automated system, observing the varying score of learners and measuring the effectiveness of the Readlee app in teaching, improving and assessing of reading skills of ESL learners at the college level. To achieve the set research targets, the learners were given a reading task and their performances were recorded and analyzed through the Readlee app. The app provided us with complete information about students' reading performance including fluency, login time/date and words assigned, words read per minute and total reading time. The findings indicated that all the students performed at varying levels according to their reading practice and background knowledge. Furthermore, the research indicated that the Readlee app is effective if it is used to teach, improve and assess reading skills of the ESL learners at the college level.

11. Significance of the Study

The current study is significant in several ways. Firstly, it solved the issue of assessing reading pace objectively. Secondly, it showed students' results at varying levels and thirdly, it indicated that the use of the Readlee app is effective in teaching assessing and improving the reading skills of college-level ESL learners. Previously, reading assessment and reading practice in the classroom were difficult because of different factors of which large-sized class was the most vital. But the current study has provided us with the solution to the previous problems in the area of reading.

12. Future Research

Currently, the use of Readlee has been tested at the college level but English language teachers in Pakistan and other countries of the world can test it at other levels of language learning. The current study has focused only on reading pace and fluency, but other researchers can use this app for many other purposes depending on their needs and requirements.

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